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COMMUNICATIONS IN THE ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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In today's economic climate, a company's effectiveness depends on the quality of its management, which is impossible without a well-established communication system within the company. Communication is a fundamental component of management, ensuring mutual understanding between managers and employees, timely management decisions, the formation of corporate culture and a positive image for the company.

The relevance of the study lies in the fact that in the context of digitalisation, growing competition and information overload, the communication system of an enterprise needs constant improvement. McKinsey research shows that the introduction of communication technologies can increase labour productivity by 20-25% [1]. Ineffective communication leads to reduced productivity, loss of customers and a deterioration in the socio-psychological microclimate within the team.

The communication process includes elements such as the sender, the message, the transmission channel and the receiver. Their effectiveness depends on the accuracy of understanding between the participants. In public administration, the process should not only ensure the exchange of information, but also form a deep understanding of it.

Various types of communication are used in business. Depending on the direction of information flow, there are vertical, horizontal and diagonal communications [2, 3]. By form of transmission, there are oral, written, visual and electronic communications. By organisational feature, there are formal and informal communications.

Modern communication management is an independent type of special management that involves the understanding and use of the patterns of exchange of

**СЕКЦІЯ. ЦИФРОВІ ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЇ В СФЕРІ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТУ ТА МАРКЕТИНГУ:
ВИКЛИКИ, ЗАГРОЗИ ТА ТРЕНДИ РОЗВИТКУ**

information, knowledge and intellectual property. Its goal is to achieve effective results in the functioning of the economic system.

Traditional methods (surveys or questionnaires), specialised methods for digital communications and the KPI system are used to evaluate effectiveness. Establishing key metrics allows companies to create a more engaged workforce.

An analysis of the communication system at Global Logistic LLC revealed the following problems that negatively affect the communication process: imperfect internal communications, outdated technologies, lack of transparency with partners, insufficient cybersecurity, and information overload. The average time for information transfer between departments was 2.5 hours, with the norm being up to 1 hour. The use of social media within the company can reduce the time spent searching for information by 35% [3]. To improve this situation, it is recommended to introduce a unified digital platform, modernise systems, strengthen cybersecurity, and develop transparent communication mechanisms and improve employee competence.

An analysis for 2022-2024 showed positive dynamics (Table 1). Order processing time was reduced by 43%, internal delays by 60%, and staff satisfaction with their work increased from 62% to 83%.

Table 1 – Dynamics of communication system indicators at Global Logistic LLC

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Years</i>		
	<i>2022</i>	<i>2023</i>	<i>2024</i>
Average order processing time, hours.	8,5	6,2	4,8
Number of internal delays, cases/month.	25	18	10
Number of customer complaints	30	22	15
Staff satisfaction level with their work, %	62	70	83

Source: compiled by the author based on internal reports from Global Logistic LLC

Thus, an effective communication system is a strategic resource for an enterprise, forming the information basis for management, ensuring the speed and

accuracy of decision-making, and creating the conditions for the development of corporate culture and increasing the competitiveness of the enterprise.

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ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ ВЗАЄМОЗВ'ЯЗКУ ПОКАЗНИКІВ ЯКОСТІ ВАНТАЖНИХ АВТОМОБІЛЬНИХ ПЕРЕВЕЗЕНЬ

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З розвитком ринкових відносин та науково-технічного прогресу з'явилися нові проблеми у сфері організації перевезень автомобільним транспортом [1]:

– проблема якості транспортного обслуговування при перевезеннях як вантажів, і пасажирів (за кордоном спеціалізованих автомобілів до 90 %, тут – приблизно 50 %);

– збереження кількості та якості вантажів у процесі перевезення, підвищення швидкості доставки, доставка точно у призначений термін;

– проблема регулярності перевезень (створення безперервної системи транспортування вантажів та пасажирів, основною метою функціонування якої є своєчасне та повне задоволення потреб народного господарства та населення у перевезеннях);

– проблема організації та безпеки руху (удосконалення автомобіля та організації руху, у тому числі ізоляція потоків пішоходів від транспортних